

mutual dependence.

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Anatatsiya: *be active functional exercise complete any physical body at a much higher level o' - check-in passengers associated with it. So "training downloads" refers to the additional activity of the body. The activity will require a certain amount of spending power in excess of the body (this size is related to the size of the load power), this is realized the need to restore and get tired after a certain time comes to such situations to understand this article describes the wide coverage was given.*

Base phrases: *downloads, the size of downloads, severe downloads, downloads the miqdorlash types of downloads, downloads criteria.*

Power consumption and downloads come along with recovery supports the process of training to get tired, they just not only do you have full recovery, but also the ability to work in full recovery downloads submaksimal and the maximum point (superkompensatsiya) provides.

The difference is the following downloads:

- workout (commercial growth) - this character in the body of an athlete the structural-chaga provides positive changes.
- stabilized commercial - this is achieved by adaptation of the condition mustah-kamlaydi.

At the same time "lessons downloads" concept athletes exercise to the body as the level of impact, determines the level of the quantitative effect of this in the first place. Less, on average, known and high-level of downloads, it is necessary to distinguish.

Support downloads feature according to his character by practice sports exercise and competition, with the usual (for certain specialty sports) and type the offbeat, the commercial growth in the direction of the effects of strength, speed, stamina, agility, flexibility and their compounds will serve the development of the

mental strain on the body the effects are already more or less mental tension which require athletes-jasi on small, medium, significant, large to the load is distributed.

<i>Ysheclansas</i>	<i>Yuclans in the great criteria of</i>	<i>the solution be should toe'present tasks</i>
Small	Important work is the ability to a period of 1-phase (real to get tired until you started the completed work 15-20%).	Exercise with structure-qan of the achieved level to maintain to stay. Previous from the load , then the recovery process speed up to
Medium	Important ishqobiliyati period of 2-phase (real to get tired until you started the completed work 40-60%)	Exercise with chiniqqan of the achieved level to maintain the stay, the exercise of private of the task, the solution to
Significant	Hidden (kompensatsiyalangan) Chfir phase (until it started to get real tired of the work completed 60-70%)	Exercise with the structure to increase
Large	Real tired of being into the coming	Exercise with hardening to increase

Yitklamaning outer and inner sides of the respective indicator of a conditional basis to differentiate taken has been.

Downloads the outer side of - this exercise is the performance of the duration of the repetition of a training exercise, the amount of movement speed, temp, and tashilayotgan h size and weight.k.

External indicators downloads - coach and athlete directs the exercise of functions in the process determines the size of some quantitative lessons and exercises. Exercise planning and work account to use them.

Downloads of the inner side of the body that the level of involvement opportunities vazifaviy (CH, respiratory volume, blood pressure and other indicators).

Internal indicators downloads - (vazifaviy of the body, they moved indicators) of the target in accordance with the size of the load exercise, exercise shifts the body under the influence of the load dynamics allows to estimate the true athletes.

Workout downloads size-itsintensity (strain) and the volume (amount) of the result is determined.

This increase reached a certain level of downloads in a time of great can continue until then it will lead to the rapid growth of the size of the decrease or vice versa.

The size and intensity of training downloads

Size - the effect of the duration of some or many downloads and exercises, workouts, period, phase, like round is the total amount of work completed at the time.

The severe - each mode of exercise (speed, miq repeat-h drugs and.k.) the effects of the load voltage and power of large-stained.

Downloads athletes to the body only the effects of external factors (size and rapidly in the body) vegetative (system providing hayotiylik) siljishlargagina, but spiritual exercises carried out (in particular intuition) tension and muqobillashti-ruvchi depends on both the complexity of it.

Use several methods of appraisal practice of the load in the complex.

Sports-gymnastics - akrobatika snaryad and elements according to the complexity of muqobillashtiruvchi ("A", "B", "C", "D"), the group are divided into two.

The fight to them with a different amount of points according to the complexity of transfer methods will be evaluated.

Downloads importance of rest in between.

As it is known, mashqjarayoni rest get'z into gets. Rest take'zqonuniyatlarigako'raamalgaoshirilsaginamashqningtashkiliytarkibiyqismibo'l ibqoladi. O'taqisqayokiuzoqmuddatli rest get to undermine the structure of the exercise, and do not exercise enough or infringement of its main ingredients is to become the reason of excess exercise. Sport mashqida filtered so that the rest (to rest according to load and incredibly emergency) problem will arise.

The rest of the workout process performs the following two main tasks:

1-load workout will help ensure the ability to work from then.

2-to improve the effectiveness of your downloads (most preferable option) serves as one of the means.

Reduce the time you rest between exercises or multiply the total load (kumulyativ) can increase or decrease the effect.

Rest between sessions to rest early in the recovery phase is always more range should be ended, i.e. after the start of the phase, which is superkompensatsiya re (reduksiya) despite the start of the phase of stand.

The direction will depend on the duration of the recovery process, the lessons often.

Downloads among the rest to get the range of 3 types of difference;

1. A full rest get

2. The hard rest get

3. Supertiklanish

1. A full rest get – this lesson during uploads among is used. The body of completed downloads from then fully restored. This while regular downloads complete to the body full of the restoration point will provide.

2. The hard rest get – this this lesson for downloads among is used. The body of completed downloads from then certain level is restored. This while regular downloads complete to the body of the incomplete recovery point will provide you and a certain level after yuklmani performance for the sake of power is gathering.

3. Supertiklanish – this this lesson for downloads among is used. The body of completed downloads from then enough to restore not. This while regular downloads complete to the body will restore the time will leave and the next yuklmani to fulfill access with was yesterday.

Sessions in the range of the rest to take the range to be applied, first of all coach's creative approach and training volume and intensity as well as training before the established target from the task come out of the selected case is applied.

Exercises after the rest of taking 2 types of difference;

1. Active rest get

2. Stagnant rest get

1. Active rest get – lessons from after yLightroq that physical action is that sports types with the deal, that is, activity type, change if, fulfilled the action mainly physical movement consisting of will be.

Active rest get – this method exercises after the completed work volume and intensity, engaged-athletes in the body they come changes, as well as coaches and athletes of their mutual agreement and imaginative approach on the basis of selected without applied.

This type of rest you get and recovery work following consists of;

1. Sports game (volleyball, basketball at, futboll , and h.k) s with the deal
2. YLight athletics sportcha walking and running from the type of itself to the corresponding distance to the choice of walking and running
3. Swimming (present at the time of the physical position considering taking without)
4. Efforts, walk them, entertainment events fulfilled actions to perform
5. Athletes of himself or coach with their mutual agreement and imaginative approach on the basis of, various active physical action with the deal and the unconventional method in the rest to get the type of apply.

2. Slack the rest of take – from training after mental discipline with associated that are working their content taking without, activity type, change if, fulfilled the action mainly mental process consists is.

Stagnant rest get – this method exercises after the completed work volume and intensity, engaged-athletes in the body they come changes, as well as coaches and athletes of their mutual agreement and imaginative approach on the basis of selected without applied.

This type of rest you get and recovery work following consists of;

1. View with associated that work with busy, being, (Television watch to and various entertainment events direct observation or the action formed composed of the actions of the simple case in monitor)
2. Hearing with associated that work with busy, being, (Music, audio broadcasting, radio listening, spiritual south , and they come in various mental emotional

situations meyorashtirishga a positive influence executive audioyozuvlar and h.k)s.

3. Rest get and emotional influence on the executive of the restoration of the event, (sleep, massage, sauna, hot shower, take to, the book of mutoala, gipnoz and h.k) s with, busy being

4. Athletes of himself or coach with their mutual agreement and imaginative approach on the basis, various the unconventional method in the rest to get the type of apply.

Speed towards the direction of athletes, as well as muqobillashtiruvchi abilities, speed-power quality, technical skill has faster recovery after carrying the exercises.

Usually with in 2-3 days after recovery from workouts in the direction of such large downloads is completed.

If endurance training is directed to the athlete shifts generate important role in the body and therefore slower the recovery process will take place within 5-7 days.

Speed the process of recovery also depends on the level of skill and a lot of training athletes. High profile athletes in the recovery of razryaddagigaqaraganda ii and iii 1.5-3 times tezroqyakunlanadi.

The duration of the recovery process of the body, the athlete also affects the total size of personal features and downloads.

In sports, the world community of the necessity to change the style and content of advances secured in the workout process has been put to the task and the size of the load exercise in the first place, it is also planned to increase the intensity.

Workout downloads, the growth of the adaptation of athletes to increase the capacity recovery be implemented in modern vehicles, making them more sports will help you to achieve high achievements. 20-25 years ago, young athletes had a condition that currently has the capacity to become the norm. In accordance with the main loads on the different direction-and the series by emergency support, recovery time and the events two and three times the size of the interaction of exercise per day kelishtirib the opportunity to do so arises.

Today, the results from day to day in the field of physical education and sport has been updated while going for the main reason that athletes and coaches from foydalanish in conjunction with a highly efficient method of and means in the process of training, and after the usual and unusual recovery from downloads mash'ulotlardan after the effective application of the work of the organization and remains one of the main factors.

Downloads combination of the principle of systematic and rest

Downloads and physical education in the process of systemic combination is a very important rule to the rest, the training effect of a general whose lotni eventually the effects will be associated to it. Between sessions of different vacation options (full, hard and superstepto langa), as well as, a large line of downloads the directions and stand management, training and frequent enough, you can achieve the maximum effect without spent with a relatively large avalanche. On top of that, the different sides of the restoration of the ability to work as a quick way geteroxron (different time) and taking into account that would occur, a weekly cycle or one-day sessions at the conclusion of the system so needless to never may not be any negative consequences and it is necessary to achieve a positive outcome.

Different systems of the body, i keep a high level of performance for a strictly defined term must complete after a break from vacation to find related downloads.

Downloads among the rest of the range was a long time to get, re-adaptation occurs – the body may return to the previous level. When the range is short of the holidays, he does not restore the body's ability to work.

Go to regular downloads the full repeat conditions tiklanmaslik reserve's reduction will lead to decline as a result of the departure of the body to work. Earlier this occur in the physiological range and extremely deep mashqlanganlikka feathers andologik those instances can lead to. Supertiklanish (superqoplanish) would be required to appear in the phase of the time range is optimal. In all cases only optimal physical and nurturing the quality of the use according to the purpose of the break vacation.

Number depending on the situation, certain bir in times full, also shortened to “hard” on a break can be helpful.

Thus, in the system of physical education clear and “leave a trail” rule taking into account the systematic effects of the sequence of combination of downloads and the conclusion is specific to the implementation of the principle to rest. The implementation of the principle explained in the same ways the following methods:

- a repetition of assignments at reasonable;
- Downloads by a combination of rational and rest;
- variantlilik assignments and should be repeated and the will of downloads.

That develops in-gradually increases the effect of the principle of mashqlantiruvchi go

This improvement at the expense of the principle tasks involved in trying to raise and downloads and boosts the opportunity to go regularly to the requirements of activity are associated with manifest psixik determines necessary.

The functional activities of the human body requirements for borilsagina regularly boosts the physical quality grows up. Strength, durability and other physical characteristics of the organism on the basis of the mechanisms of the development of functional adaptation in response to specific changes in the physical to share downloads of lies. Optimal selection of the downloads is very important, that is, the adaptation of the organism which produces minimal downloads severe reactions should know. Excessive strain or also more severe effects, power requirements, moderately's activities will lead to the composition of the body. Identify, for example, the average adult weight in athletes with large and close to going now also grow in power when doing exercises. In this case the big Downloads and be ready to pick up of many organ systems (heart-vascular system, the musculoskeletal apparatus of the joints) in adults and in order to avoid excessive strain on close to no sense of being used for large downloads. It is fair to say, has a different effect on various organs of the system of High Downloads. Fast downloads and the top of one of them is able to withstand relatively easy to some, others – on the contrary. Thus, functional changes faster, more slowly morphological changes was the night. The dynamics of the physical system in the body and increase downloads geteroxron in some way due to the features and level of adaptation should be.

Improving movement skills qualifications on the basis of terms of implementation, to ensure that every time to fit the changing requirements of the system lies in the different functional process. Therefore, this system is the main condition of the form – changing and complex routine tasks go on the requirements of the act and increase studied.

So, that develops-mashqlantiruvchi gradually increases the effect of bobrowsing the principle of difficult assignments to go with them increased and update the plan to go to the functional options of the organism are growingI just downloads implies the increase of size and intensity.

The principle of the balance of dynamics personalized downloads.

So out came the three main rules of this principle, according to them the total Downloads of the dynamics of typical forms identified within the stage of physical education.

1. The total amount should be used in the process of physical education of downloads, so that his negative health indications of a changeworkto should not be produced. The effectiveness of these rules to control the regular kumulyativ of the downloads is provided.
2. Go to downloads and adapted to be used towards that, that is, adapted to the last stage as the total Downloads stable condition changes the size ofthe regular completion of s should be done.

The level of training achieved is much higher if the parameters are so large that downloads.

3. In physical education lessons from some of its stages, the amount of total downloads of a temporary reduction in the use of the system, or be stabilized, or increased, which implies that temporary.

The number of sessions

11-graph. The dynamics of the amount of total downloads in physical education's forms

- I - stradella in a straight line;
- II - zinasimon stradella;
- III - to'lqinsimon stradella.

The above comments from the form of the dynamics in the amount of two physical education total downloads: zinasimon stradella stradella and is the basis for the use of the form to'lqinsimon. In general, a straight line across from stradella dynamics also use downloadswill be sa (9-graph). However, the very short time that is the stage inthe rage you can use.

The principle of the conclusion of a cycle of sessions

In this process of physical education – cyclo to the generated classes and the stage is locked into that. Accordingly ajaratiladi three types: mikrotsikllar

(weekly), and at the same time each of them repeated the same exercise they have to be applied orientation, and characterized by a combination with the rest of the downloads; mezotsikllar (monthly), two of them include six mikrotsikllarni of life in them, the amount of tools, the combination of the ratio of and the procedure varies; makrotsikllar (annual), they will last a long time which stage in the process of physical education in amalis carried by.

These principles of physical education and sports of the staff tugallab of the cycle and taking into account within them, as well as lessons thatmulyativ growing that the effect of the physical education general education general and special rivojlantirilishini go and going for that taking into account to establish a system of training and directs the series.

The principle of corresponding areas of physical education to the age of

The direction of the human body, the principles of physical training thatispecific to your age (pre-school, small, medium, large) physical development, that is, corresponding to a period of changing ontogenez ravishdaizchil puts the commitment to change.

Physical education is the process of going up to the age of the particular period should be provided to the physical effects on the overall body. This action and the formation of a wide range of skills and qualifications to the operation of comprehensive physical development finds its expression. During this period the school in raising the quality of the physical principles of this or that man's physical attributes of the zones that appear the most favorable opportunities for the development of the intuition, consider taqozo is.

Sharpen the first age, and adolescence (taxmine under the age of 35) reveals favorable opportunities for full realization of the body's functional capabilities. For many in the form of prolonged physical education in the direction of general physical preparation will be. For the age of adolescence is very active in sports to engage and achieve high results on the basis of its specific.

In adulthood, this second direction during the period of stabilization of the functional capabilities of physical education achieved good work ability, their physical participates as to keep the level of training achieved.

Much more in the late period (women over the age of 55, men - over the age of 60) human health implications of physical education will help to show

resistance to various negative factors. Deal with physical training physical exercise-recovery feature will be able to.

Can you say in general, the areas of physical education for many years with the principle of corresponding to the age of physical education exercise most importantly is in the process of going from use.

The review reflects the principles of physical education and holistic qonuniyat different side of the process. They complement each other and mutually bound is the summary of fundamental methodological rules, but the unit is made up of. The whole complex of physical education tamoyildanchekinish any process upset and can cause them to become almost ineffective the teacher and student of the great labor.

References

1. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Sportda murabbiylik faoliyatining psixologik tadqiqoti. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157) , 1 (9), 344–352.
2. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). SPORT, ESTETIKA VA ESTETIK TARBIYA. Sharqiy akademik va ko‘p tarmoqli tadqiqotlar jurnali , 1 (3), 82-89.
3. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg‘ulotlari sog‘lom turmush tarzining ajralmas qismidir. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157) , 1 (9), 338-343.
4. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Harakat malakalarini shakllantirishning fiziologik asoslari va sport texnikasini o‘rgatish. E'tiqod va madaniyatning kesishgan joylari: Amerika diniy va madaniyat tadqiqotlari jurnali (2993-2599) , 1 (9), 87-94.
5. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). JISMONIY TARBIYA DARSLARINING MAZMUNI-AHAMIYATI VA TAMOYILLARI
6. Saidova, MA (2023). BO'SH VAQTDA QILADIGAN SPORTNING Stress VA SALOMATLIKGA TA'SIRI. Umumjahon fanlari bo'yicha ta'lim tadqiqotlari , 2 (11), 294–299.
7. Saidova, M. A. (2023). SPORT VA FALSAFANING ALOQASI. SALOMATLIKGA TA'SIRI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 288-293.

8. Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). The Initial Exercise of Teaching Methodology to Gymnastics . American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 329–337.

9. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). Sport gimnastika mashg'ulotlarida asosiy harakat qobilyat (FMS), postural (muvozanat) nazorat va o'zini o'zi idrok etishga sport gimnastikasining ta'sir. Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research , 1(3), 74-81.

10. Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich Sayfiyev. (2023). The Place of Gymnastics in A Person's Life and the Terms Used in Training. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 353–359.

11. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Use of Acrobatic Exercises and Their Terms In The Process of Teaching Gymnastics. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(9), 80–86.

12. Сайфиёв, Х., & Саидова, М. (2023). БАДМИНТОНИСТЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКИЙ ПОДГОТОВКА И ЕМУ РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДЫ. Инновационные исследования в науке, 2(4), 45-54.

13. Sayfiyev , H. X. (2023). SPORT GIMNASTIKASI ORQALI YOSH BOLLALARNING HARAKAT KO'NIKMASI RIVOJLANTIRISH PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 300–306.

14. Ayubovna, S. M., & Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). YOSH BOLLALARDA SPORT SPORT GIMNASTIKASINING PEDAGOGIK O'LCHOVLAR NAZARIYASI VA TASHKILY-METODIK ASOSLARINI TADQIQ ETISHNING MAQSADI, VAZIFALARI. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS, 2(22), 108-118.

15. Saidova, M. (2023). Jismoniy SIFATLAR TUSHUNCHASI. Zamonaviy fan va tadqiqotlar , 2 (10), 251–254.

16. Saidova, M. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 251-254.

17. Ayubovna, S. M., & Komiljonova, K. I. (2022). Features of Application of Sports Games in Preschool Children. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 16, 17-23.

18. Saidova, M., & Sayfiyev , H. (2023). CONTENT-IMPORTANCE AND PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 192–199.

19. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Acrobat exercise and sports gymnastika sessions through the power of development method. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 460–467.

20. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Methods and methods of teaching sports gymnastics in young boles. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 453–459.

21. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical attributes (capabilities) of development of the main legality. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 2(12), 373–380.

22. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). RESEARCH METHODS OF YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

23. Ikromova Sitora Akbarovna. (2023). NEUROPHYSIOLOGY BASIS OF HORMONES. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 68–77.

24. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information in Adolescents. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 119-122.

25. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONSCIOUSNESS AND THE TEACHING OF CONCEPTS OF THE UNCONSCIOUS TO STUDENTS. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 107-114.

26. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). Cognitive processes and their description in psychology. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 115-133.

27. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 184-191.

28. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE CHANGES IN ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOR. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 192-197.

29. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN ADOLESCENTS. *Innovation in Science, Education and Technology*.

30. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023). Capabilities of SPSS Software in High Volume Data Processing Testing. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 82-86.

31. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023, November). IDENTIFYING THE POSITIVE EFFECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL WORK FACTORS BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS AND DEPARTMENTS THROUGH SPSS SOFTWARE. *In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 18, pp. 150-153).

32. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). TEACHING THE BASICS OF PYTHON PROGRAMMING. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11).

33. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). Solving Complex Problems in Python. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education* (2993-2769), 1(9), 481-484.

34. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DATA PROCESSING USING THE SPSS PROGRAM. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 2(23), 220-223.

35. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). ADVANTAGES OF DJANGO FEMWORKER. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

36. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PYTHON (PYTORCH). *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 123-126.

37. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). SPSS YOKI IJTIMOIY FANLAR UCHUN STATISTIK PAKET BILAN PSIXOLOGIK MA'LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 207–215.

38. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). THE MECHANISMS OF USING MATHEMATICAL STATISTICAL ANALYSIS METHODS IN PSYCHOLOGY. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 138-144.

39. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES, THEIR TYPES AND BASICS. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 145-152.

40. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PYTHON TILINING AFZALLIKLARI VA KAMCHILIKLARI. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 153-159.

41. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PYTHON DASTUR TILIDADA WEB-ILOVALAR ISHLAB CHIQISH. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 160-166.

42. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). SUN'IY INTELLEKTDADA PYTHONNING (PYTORCH) KUTUBXONASIDAN FOYDALANISH. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 167-171.

43. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). WORKING WITH MATHEMATICAL FUNCTIONS IN PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 172-177

